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By an eccentric whim of fate or on a centripetal tip from above?

*(Alternate title: **Dispelling energetic darkness & material murk**)*

**По эксцентричной прихоти судьбы или же по централизованной наводке
свыше?**

*(Альтернативное название или, возможно, подзаголовок: «**Развеивая
энергетическую тьму и материальный мрак**»)*

**Taqdirning injiq injiqligi bilanmi yoki yuqoridan kelgan markazlashtirilgan
rahbarlik bilanmi?**

*(Muqobil sarlavha yoki ehtimol taglavha: "**Energiya zulmatini va moddiy xiralikni
tarqatish**")*

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ABSTRACT

The discussion article offered here casts doubt on the rightness of the Breakthrough Prize Committee, which 10 years ago awarded its multi-million-dollar bonus to a triple of American astrophysicists A.G.Riess – S.Perlmutter – B.P.Schmidt. Although let's still clarify: in this case we are not talking about a technical faults in measuring the color spectrum or luminosity of the fuzzy supernovae (which they directly dealt with), but about the subsequent too free interpretation of obtained results, that ultimately led to a general dominant influence of the term "dark energy".

However, besides, the author in his article also makes a bold attempt to debunk (or, at least, a little "to ground") one more eternal mind-disturbing cosmic mystery, connected with the phenomenon of "silentium universi". While, to what extent he succeeded really in that - is up to you, dear readers.

And nevertheless the appropriate conclusion obviously suggests here itself: when unraveling the most difficult outlook problems of cosmology, it is better to trust, of course, philosophers rather than naturalists or techies!

Keywords: SETI-project, the global Universe's acceleration, pranophytes, dark energy, dark matter, quasi-anthropic paradox, chrono-sacredness of being.

По эксцентричной прихоти судьбы или же по централизованной наводке свыше?

КРАТКАЯ АННОТАЦИЯ

Предлагаемая здесь вашему вниманию дискуссионная статья ставит под сомнение правоту и объективность международного комитета премии «Прорыв», который 10 лет назад присудил свою многомиллионную награду тройке американских астрофизиков А.Г.Рисс – С.Перлмуттер – Б.П.Шмидт. Хотя все же уточним: речь в данном случае идет не о технических погрешностях в измерении цветового спектра или яркости некоторых блеклых сверхновых (с которыми они непосредственно имели дело), а о последующей чересчур вольной трактовке полученных результатов, что в конечном итоге привело ко всеобщей доминирующей экспансии термина «темная энергия». Однако, кроме этого, автор в своей статье предпринимает также и довольно смелую попытку развенчать (или, по крайней мере, хоть немного «приземлить») еще одну веками тревожащую наши умы космическую тайну, связанную с феноменом «Silentium Universi». Ну а насколько ему это удалось – судить уж вам, уважаемые коллеги.

Но всё ж таки заключительный вывод напрашивается, пожалуй, тут как бы сам собою: решение наиболее сложных и запутанных проблем космологии лучше, конечно же, доверять философам, а не естественникам или технарям!

Ключевые слова: проект SETI, глобальное вселенское ускорение, пранофиты, темная энергия, темная материя, квазиантропный парадокс, хроно-

сакральность бытия.

Taqdirning g'ayrioddiy injiqligi bilanmi yoki yuqoridan markazlashtirilgan uchidami?

Abstrakt

Bu erda taqdim etilgan muhokama maqolasi 10 yil oldin o'zining ko'p million dollarlik bonusini amerikalik astrofiziklar A.G.Riess - S.Perlmutter - B.P.Shmidt uchliklariga topshirgan "Breakthrough" mukofoti qo'mitasining to'g'riligiga shubha tug'diradi. Hali ham aniqlik kiritaylik: bu holda biz loyqa o'ta yangi yulduzlarning rang spektrini yoki yorqinligini o'lchashdagi texnik nosozliklar haqida emas (ular bilan bevosita buni qilardilar), balki olingan natijalarni keyinchalik haddan tashqari erkin talqin qilish haqida, bu oxir-oqibatda "qorong'u energiya" atamasining umumiy dominant ta'siri.

Biroq, bundan tashqari, muallif o'z maqolasida "silentium universi" fenomeni bilan bog'liq yana bir abadiy ongni bezovta qiluvchi kosmik sirni ochishga (yoki, hech bo'lmaganda, "pastroq erga" bir oz) dadil harakat qiladi. Xo'sh, u qanchalik bunga erishdi, siz hukm qilasiz, aziz hamkasblar.

Ammo baribir, yakuniy xulosa, ehtimol, o'z-o'zidan o'zini ko'rsatadi: kosmologiyaning eng qiyin dunyoqarash muammolarini hal qilishda, tabiiyki, tabiatshunoslar yoki texniklarga emas, balki faylasuflarga ishonish yaxshiroqdir!

***Kalit so'zlar:** SETI-loyiha, global koinot tezlashishi, pranofitlar, qorong'u energiya, qorong'u materiya, kvazi-antropik paradoks, borliqning xrono-muqaddaslik.*

Introductory part

The freshest widely publicized successes of overseas theorists who have by guess "studied" the first seconds after the Big Bang through orbiting telescopes and nuclear colliders, along with pride in modern world science, cannot but evoke in you and me a bit of sound skepticism about their activities.

For such a zero retropolation often, alas, contradicts many accepted logical postulates. In particular, if long-term forecasts are anyway built usually thanks to the sufficient availability of 100% proven archived facts, then it is still not entirely clear, what speculative "peeping" into pre-human history can be based on. Hence, one

shouldn't, as it were, be extra surprised at the abundance of various false moves and other misbeliefs (like torsion fields' memorable insanity), by the spontaneous witnesses of which most of us had a chance to become. Wherein some experts frankly assess the today stalemate uncertainty as a kind of creative stagnation; second are inclined towards the version of consumerity-driven global theoretical shift; while third directly declare that it is time for representatives of the exact sciences, obviously, to prepare for the change of the old starry paradigm to cardinally updated.

1. Under an oppressive mute marquee.

As firsthand confirmed by the sad experience of Carl Sagan [1, p. 11-13] [2, p. 16-18], Seth Shostak [3, p. 381], Jill Tarter, Victor Schwartzman [4, p.184], Gregory Beskin [5, p.186] and other active SETI-researchers [6] [7, p. 690], all five options of the modern interpretation of "grande silentium universi", alas, may turn out to be untenable without involving a number of additional entities. So, let's briefly recall them here.

1) *Life is an extremely rare phenomenon.* (Parried by the data of paleocosmonautics and, in particular, the presence of bacteria in meteorites.)

2) *All civilizations eventually come to hedonism.* (However both the banal consumerity and the notorious hedonism can hardly be regarded in the form of some persistent attribute of public shapings: unless as a certain mediate stage in the structuring of the intelligent Universe).

3) *All civilizations available today are non-technogenic.*

4) *All civilizations sooner or later come to self-destruction.*

5) *Though life as such is widespread throughout the Space, but on a whim of fate, our civilization was the initial (or at least the second) in this "happy-scroll".*

However, with the postulating an extra-material god, the 3rd and 5th versions can even so find a quite reasonable explanation here. In addition, item 5 entirely fits into the anthropogeocentric platform. And since the existence of high powers is indirectly confirmed by many other mysterious artifacts, then god-presence (in relation to i.5) can be interpreted transcendently: say, as a manifestation of some parallel worlds or the "soft" dictate (seeming to us unobtrusive at all) of a priori sacralized Chronos i.e., to put it simply - time. Let's note, by the way, the last thing is also equivalent to the statement of overwhelming astrological dependence. At that, these are not even two sides of a single coin but in general two completely tantamount definitions of the same phenomenon. And among other things, such a qualitative converting of the dominated spatio-temporal paradigm would certainly help to deal

with the notorious "dark energy", which actually does not exist at all. By the way, in more detail this will be discussed in the final section of this publication.

Thus, now the question on the immediate agenda is whether individualized high powers like UFO-nauts, angels, white & black tengri [8], jinnees, cherubs and similar demigods (united – according to the author - under a common name of “pranophytes”) really sit in the nature. For the presence of the supreme extra-material substance doesn't already cause, probably, any doubts: without it planetary progress would have been simply impossible. However such pranophytes can be imagined both in the kind of collection of special elementary particles and in the form of diverse wave emanations, let alone infusions of some spiritualized energy from parallel worlds [9, p.420] [10]. Shortly speaking, this purely outlook question is still relevant to us - despite the fact that higher superindividuals almost never interfere in everyday aspects of social life (not to mention someone's concrete human destinies).

But generally, it makes sense to talk now about 3 principled dynamic schemes of universe:

a) a sort of swing "from energy (Will) to information (Reason) and back";

b) continuous experiments or even improvisations of the Will itself (by the by, the old theosophical teaching about the before predominated 5 lightly-built races also fits into here);

c) and as if independently of them, a fashionable new-minted hypothesis about our existence sicut a computer simulation of the physical world can be considered too (moreover, in this case, bits and bytes well familiar to IT-specialists become already the main source of interplay [11, p. 243-255] of all real-virtual objects).

At that, any productive actions of the Cosmic Intelligence should, in theory, be determined by the suitable characteristics of its elementary carriers (informons): namely, self-doubling or contactless transmission of some inner parameters. What together allows them to bypass the notorious no-go on cloning (introduced into modern scientific practice by William Wootters, Wojciech Zurek and Dennis Dieks), and also most of similar inconsistencies associated with violation of parity & chirality.

Therein lies the principal difference between such mobile and unwearied micro-particles and the “holy spirit”, which is based (even if, for example, one identify it with a certain gauge field) on weightless strictly virtual bosons or, possibly, superluminal tachyons. In addition, it isn't excluded that presented to us from above energy (as, in substance, Universe's Time either) can't be broken down into the smallest discrete components at all, since is de-facto an attribute, not object and especially tool of a

harmonious divine world order. Which in turn, acting as the root cause for any type of physical interplays, gives a creative impetus to overall evolutionary progress [12].

2. From ancient hoary superstition to a full-fledged branch of knowledge that is greatly authoritative and demanded today.

Thus, having analyzed what was said, you may come to quite sound and natural conclusion regarding the obvious etiological relationship of informons with dark matter. Well and, accordingly, it would be most reasonable to liken gravitational lenses and invisible compact halos to some local noospheres, per se tied to their motherly galaxies. At that, the chief claimants to the role of elementary carriers of intelligence, if we talk about really existing particles, are the lightest currently known leptons - neutrinos (and among the hypothetical ones - for instance, WIMPs or LSP). However, in general, all of them are considered stable, whereas in given case this quality by no means is mandatory. Especially that the option with self-doubling of informons (when transmitting relevant useful data) may well be comparable to their self-disintegration*. Which, in turn, significantly expands the horizon of searching for adequate candidates!..

But on the whole, seemingly polarity of interests of the Reason and the Will is actually felt except, perhaps, in the socio-historical plane. While in all the rest, they go near, as if complementing each other; and moreover at the supremacy of Reason for now. In this way, here it would be admissible (and even then - on Universe's scale) their principled opposing only in terms of time parameters: from the energy of saturated but structureless chaos - to an extremely structured but cold-lifeless Cosmos. And just at this finish segment, due to the critical shortage of natural resources, the energy-dependent transition to the hegemony of robots is looked a quite practicable.

Well and also here it should be noted that, relying on the anthropogeocentric foundation, it turns out to be much easier to substantiate the very essence of unique prophecies too. So, for example, in the first of the above paragraphs ("swing/pendulum"), such super-vision is possible thanks to the everlasting Universal circulation, and in the second - through the management of optimal for the Will scenario. As for another speculative idea – concerning allegedly spontaneous penetration into parallel worlds (or, say, multidimensional space) - it doesn't, all appearances, jump beyond these boundaries but unless introduces here some own colorful variety conditioned by the likely presence of the end-to-end ontological memory.

That is, the ability to clairvoyantness may well not be directly associated with those rare sensational miracles we are already accustomed imperceptibly to (or about which, at least, have been hearing more than enough). For the seers contemplate not the coming perspective itself, but only astral expansion somehow coupled with it (even if they borrow all the required information from celestial contact-agents). This opinion is also confirmed by numerous cases from the life of twins which, developing “ex uno ovo materno”, have accordingly a joint astral line (as a result of that are then subjected to almost identical vicissitudes of fate). And from this, in turn, it follows that aforesaid metaphysical lever has the greatest impact on the subconscious thoughts and many involuntary movements of person.

Thus, astrology in its essence is by no means reduced to a banal copying of various Universe's cycles. But even if it can be done, then ipso facto time itself ought to have some special transcendental qualities that would determine its interest in certain objects. After all, no matter what they say, any babe, apparently from conception, is already organically connected with heaven through invisible strong bonds, therefore the theosophical notion about the astral as one of the influential "subtle sheaths" has, by and large, its complete right to exist.

In turn, the meaningfulness or, for example, spirituality of time as if dominating over space, is a fairly tempting, in principle, idea either, that saves us, by the way, from the obligatoriness of the astral microsphere. And yet, within the authorial hypothesis [13, p.10-13] «Earth is the hub of Universe" (or, as an option, religious: "man is the crown of creation"), everything quite can be determined by only configuration of stellar ensembles.

It is curious that the heaven selectively shows its sympathy-antipathy for specific individuals (and sometimes even for entire countries) precisely at the level of luck or, in extreme cases, the basic vital instincts; but at all, however, do not regulate the degree of their mental abilities. This once again emphasizes the ancient evolutionary nature of such connections - as, incidentally, that mankind is little by little getting rid of them (and in a robotic society they, in substance, will finally lose any relevance).

But still, whatever it was, knowing the results of the prophecy (whether from the mouth of a palmist, parapsychologist or even simple gypsy fortune-teller), with a strong own desire those can, of course, be prevented! Thereby, all the common pseudoscientific speculations on this theme [14, p.80-85] [15] (arbitrarily taken, for example, from biographies of Napoleon Bonaparte, queen Marie Antoinette, A.S. Pushkin, M.S. Gorbachov, Indira & Rajiv Gandhi, Donald Trump and others) do not have serious evidence grounds.

The resumptive summary.

So, what useful for science conclusions can be drawn from this?

Well, first of all, the old battered idea of the chrono-sacred nature of being is quite capable, obviously, to find here a new weighty portion of incentive bonuses. For in itself, the one-pointedness of the arrow of time fundamentally runs counter to all our principles of mundane logic based anyway on practically everywhere observed attributive symmetry of the type "plus-minus", "left-right", "better-worse", "larger-lesser", "upwards-downwards", "forward-back" (i.e. it's as if inaccessible a priori to meaningful perception)**.

In this regard, it's much simpler for man-made electronic devices (say. computers or robots): for them time is just so absolute empty abstraction as other commonplace parameters initially put by the coder into their BIOS. And that is why, completely ignoring the lamented Heraclitean maxim about the impossibility of entering the same river twice, techies easily like nibbling sun-seeds execute programmatic recovery to the optimal status quo at the slightest need. While any desperate attempts of the oligarchs to gain so desire for themselves immortality, on the contrary, are doomed to an inevitable fiasco - no matter how refined the ultra-modern stem procedures used in this case may be. And all - because of stubborn resistance on the part of the individual astral that is once and forever attached to us, providing a person with a sense of time, but ultimately taking in exchange life.

As for another urgent & eternal topic "grande silentium universi", here the situation also, frankly speaking, requires truly serious philosophical approach.

If, according to Drake's formula [16] [17]:

$$N = R \cdot f_p \cdot n_c \cdot f_l \cdot f_i \cdot f_e \cdot L$$

there should be a dozen highly developed alien communities in the not so, seemingly, remote fields of the Milky Way, and such, alas, are none at all, then a trite Laplacian justification doesn't work here. That is, more specifically, this may indicate one of three options:

I) the etiological complexity of the origin of civilizations associated with the nonlinearity of the paths "from inanimate to living" (which, as it were, is confirmed by the spread version of the five discarnate races that preceded us);

II) a certain planning of space exploration (but this obviously requires the creative participation of some almighty Scheduler!);

III) a good location of our home planet near the very neck of the multiverse.

The first of these assumptions belongs to the theosophical school, while the second represents the cornerstone idea of orthodox Christianity. And only the last of the items gives a general holistic notion of a new, rather original way of settling the Fermi paradox [18, p.40-41]. Moreover just in this variant, the so-called mystery of dark energy (which in many respects, it turns out, is due to choice of the spatial point of coordinates by actively contemplating subject himself) can be solved without peculiar difficulties. For on the periphery of topologically closed Universe, any non-biased observer won't already find a single dark erg or even an extra electron-volt in this case. After all, authorial concept, besides that, unambiguously states an illusory nature of "the global acceleration" ostensibly recorded by the nimble American-Jewish trinity Riess & Perlmutter & Schmidt [19, p. 50—57].

** By the way, the recently discovered process of neutrino oscillations, in which the most relevant for us electron neutrinos are temporarily donning the guise of their closest tribesmen (taon, muon ones, etc.), fits well into this.*

*** However, at the microcosm level, that's not excluded, the course of time may differ from how we experience it in daily realities: for example, by greater symmetry about the starting point, when the happenings "before that" and "after" are much easier to calculate than in normal situation (although one could here add, by and large, the phenomenon of equally probable interconversions of virtual particles). But still maintaining, nonetheless, of the unshakable principle of time irreversibility, conditioned and synchronously oriented along the fundamental entropic vector!*

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